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Brief Survey of Facial Expression Recognition Using Subspace Methods

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Abstract

Facial Expression recognition using subspace processing involves a sequence of actions on the image data and the generation of output which gives the performance range of recognition. By contrast, real time recognition of facial expression systems using subspace methods is often event driven with minimal feature extraction data processing. In this paper dimensionality reduction subspace analysis are illustrated. Extraction of feature depends on dimensionality reduction vectors which gives the comparison information's required for classifying the various facial expression images. Emotion variations can be analyzed using subspace methods. This brief survey gives differences between various subspace methods.

Keyword: Subspace, Facial expression recognition, Principal component, Independent component

1) Introduction

Subspace methods are more efficient for both dimension reduction and projection of face images. In facial expression recognition subspace analysis makes major role for finding various features [1]. Process of reducing the number of variables under observation is one of the properties of subspace analysis. Usually the vector constructed by face image is considered to lie in a high-dimensional vector space. In the context of face recognition images of faces, represented as high-dimensional pixel arrays, often belong to a manifold of intrinsically low dimension [6]. Facial expression recognition, and computer vision research in general, has witnessed a growing interest in techniques that capitalize on this observation and apply algebraic and statistical tools for extraction and analysis of the underlying manifold[3]. In this paper, we describe in roughly chronologic order techniques that identify, parameterize, and analyze linear and nonlinear subspaces methods.

2) Appearance Based Dimensionality Reduction Subspace Methods

Time and space complexity are two main problems for certain task in image processing and pattern recognition. Hence in order to overcome this problem dimensionality reduction methods are used. The various linear and non-linear appearance based dimensionality reduction and subspace algorithms have been studied in detail with their properties and its applications in this research work. Literature survey is carried out on various subspace methods like Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Fisher Face Analysis (FF), Independent Component Analysis (ICA), Singular Value Decomposition (SVD)[26], Locality Preserving Projections (LPP), this study led to compare the above algorithms with facial expression recognition by extracting different features and evaluating the different face recognition parameters. The difference between above algorithms has been investigated. The first step of this

research work is studying and implementing the dimensionality reduction algorithms like PCA, ICA, SVD, LPP, FF, for different facial expression public database images. Secondly, face recognition across different facial expressions using score level fusion methods using existing subspace methods are tested with facial expression database and public databases.

a. Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

While PCA is commonly used to project face patterns from a high dimensional image space to a lower dimensional feature space, a drawback of this approach is that it defines a subspace such that it has the greatest variance of the projected sample vectors among all the subspaces. However, such projection is not suitable for classification since it may contain principal components which retain unwanted large variations [12].

It is a component based statistical subspace method used in facial expression recognition system to transform high dimensionality image data into low dimensionality image data to save memory space and to increase the speed of face recognition. Dimensionally reduced data is called subspace. The main purpose of using PCA is to find vectors that are best account for variation of facial expressions in face images in the entire space of images are called components. These vectors components are called eigenvectors. PCA is used to project the spaces that give significant variations among known face images. The significant features variants are called eigenfaces. Basically these eigenvectors and eigenvalues are of the covariance matrix. To reconstruct the images largest eigenvectors and eigenvalues are used. Eigenvectors are the coordinate values that defines directions of the axes whose length are given by the eigenvalues. PCA method is useful in feature extraction at constant illumination conditions[11].

Dimensionality reduction or subspace representation and feature extraction of face image using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) method is implemented on public database. Evaluation steps of subspace methods and face recognition databases are illustrated below.

PCA Algorithm

I. Training Phase

Step 1: Compute the average face

Consider a square image with width=height = N from image database, M is the total number of images in training database and P is the number of persons in the database (number of classes).Let us consider two images from four classes with different facial expressions.

	$c = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 & c_i \\ c_4 & c_5 \\ c_7 & c_8 \end{bmatrix}$				
	$f = \begin{bmatrix} f_1 & f_2 & f_3 \\ f_4 & f_5 & f_6 \\ f_7 & f_8 & f_{N^2} \end{bmatrix}$				
	$h = \begin{bmatrix} h_1 & h_2 & h_3 \\ h_4 & h_5 & h_6 \\ h_7 & h_8 & h_{N^2} \end{bmatrix}$				

Convert these matrixes into $N \times 1$ matrix and transpose it

$$a = [a_1 \ a_2 \ a_3 \ \dots \ a_{N^2}]^T = aX1 = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ a_{N^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad b = [b_1 \ b_2 \ b_3 \ \dots \ b_{N^2}]^T = bX1 = \begin{bmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \\ b_3 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ b_{N^2} \end{bmatrix} \dots \dots \dots$$

$$\dots \dots \dots h = [h_1 \ h_2 \ h_3 \ h_4 \ h_5 \ h_6 \ h_7 \ h_8 \ h_{N^2}]^T = hX1 = \begin{bmatrix} h_1 \\ h_2 \\ h_3 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ h_{N^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

Total images in training database is $X_i = [a, b, c, d, e, f, g \dots M]$

Average face image = $\bar{m} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_i^M$

$$\bar{m} = \frac{1}{M} \begin{bmatrix} a_1 + b_1 + \dots + h_1 \\ a_2 + b_2 + \dots + h_2 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ a_{N^2} + b_{N^2} + \dots + h_{N^2} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} m_1 \\ m_2 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ m_{N^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

Step 2: Subtract the mean image from training image

$$\vec{a}_m = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 - m_1 \\ a_2 - m_2 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ a_{N^2} - m_{N^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad \vec{b}_m = \begin{bmatrix} b_1 - m_1 \\ b_2 - m_2 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ b_{N^2} - m_{N^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad \dots \dots \dots \quad \vec{h}_m = \begin{bmatrix} h_1 - m_1 \\ h_2 - m_2 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ h_{N^2} - m_{N^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

Step 3: Build a matrix A which is N^2 by M dimension

$$A = [\vec{a}_m \ \vec{b}_m \ \vec{c}_m \ \vec{d}_m \ \vec{e}_m \ \vec{f}_m \ \vec{g}_m \ \vec{h}_m]$$

Step 4: Compute the Covariance matrix

Compute the covariance matrix $C = AA^T$, it is a large matrix hence its computation is very high it is a N^2 by N^2 matrix.

Step 5: Compute the Eigenvalues and Eigenvectors

Find eigenvalues of the covariance matrix by reducing the dimensionality of covariance matrix. Compute another matrix which is M by M .

$$L = A^T A$$

Find M eigenvalues and eigenvectors of covariance matrix L , Build a matrix V from eigenvectors of L , where eigenvectors of L are linear combination of image space with the eigenvectors of L

$U = AV$ Where V is eigenvector of L represents the variations in the faces.

Step 6: Compute the Weight Matrix

A facial image can be projected in to face to 1D subspace (calculating weights only with larger eigenvalues)

Weight matrix is $W_i = [\Omega_1 \Omega_2 \dots \Omega_M]^T$

Step 7: Compute the threshold value

$$\theta = \frac{1}{2} \max\{\|\Omega_i - \Omega_j\|\} \text{ for } i, j = 1 \dots M$$

II Testing Phase

Consider a recognizing or unknown image r for testing

$$r = \begin{bmatrix} r_1 & r_2 & r_3 \\ r_4 & r_5 & r_6 \\ r_7 & r_8 & r_{N^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{or} \quad r = [r_1 \ r_2 \ r_3 \ r_4 \ r_5 \ r_6 \ r_7 \ r_8 \ r_{N^2}]^T = rX1 = \begin{bmatrix} r_1 \\ r_2 \\ r_3 \\ \vdots \\ r_{N^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\vec{r}_m = \begin{bmatrix} r_1 - m_1 \\ r_2 - m_2 \\ \vdots \\ r_{N^2} - m_{N^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

Compute the covariance matrix C , by referring above steps. Where $C = \vec{r}_m (i)$.

Consider a testing image r_m (recognizing image) repeat the step1 to step 5 as given above and calculate U . And compute the projection on to the face space.

$$W_r = U^T (\vec{r}_m)$$

Where \vec{r}_m is a average subspace image of testing image.

III Score Value calculation Phase (Classification using Euclidean distance)

Compute distance in the face space between the testing face and training face images.

$$\epsilon_i^2 = \|W_r - W_i\|^2 \text{ for all } i=1 \dots M$$

Where W_i is a vector describing the k^{th} face class of training images. If ϵ_i is less than some predefined threshold value θ_i or if $\min\{\epsilon_i\} < \theta$ then test image belongs to class i . So that recognizing image is matched with trained image.

2D

b) PCA components are in linear for 1D (subspace)

Figure 2. a) PC A component for

b. Independent Component Analysis (ICA)

Input pixel data is decorrelated by PCA method using second-order statistics and there by produces lower dimension or compressed data with minimum mean-squared re-projection error, Independent Component Analysis (ICA) subspace method minimizes both second-order and higher-order dependencies in the input signal. Its purpose is to decompose an observed signal into a linear combination of unknown independent signals. Let S be the vector of unknown source signals and X is the vector of observed mixtures. If A is the unknown mixing matrix, then the mixing model is written as

$$X = A.S$$

It is assumed that the source signals are independent of each other and the mixing matrix A is invertible. Based on these assumptions and the observed mixtures, ICA algorithms try to find the mixing matrix A or the separating matrix W , such that

$$U = W.X = W.A.S$$

It is an approximate estimation of the independent source signals of ICA can be viewed as a generalization of PCA. Sample covariance of the training data is zero because PCA method decorrelates the training data. The 2D subspace recovered by ICA appears to reflect the distribution of the data much better than the subspace obtained with PCA. Another example of an ICA basis is shown in Figure 3, which is blind source separation model. It is observed that two unordered non orthogonal IC vectors, one of which is roughly aligned with the first principal component vector. Note that the actual non-Gaussianity and statistical independence achieved in this example are minimal.

ICA Algorithm

Repeat the steps which are explained in PCA algorithm (from step 1 to step 5) and follow the steps given below.

Step 1: Compute the Weight Matrix

Estimate observed matrix $X = AS_i^T$

Where $S_i^T = [S_1, S_2, S_3, \dots, S_n]$ is a eigenvectors of covariance matrix C are considered as separating signals. The value of A is obtained from covariance matrix ie

$$A = [\vec{a}_m \ \vec{b}_m \ \vec{c}_m \ \vec{d}_m \ \vec{e}_m \ \vec{f}_m \ \vec{g}_m \ \vec{h}_m] \text{ is unknown mixing matrix}$$

Step 2: Estimation of basis image

$U = XW$ where W is separation matrix or $N \times N$ is invertible matrix of covariance matrix. Then $U^T = WX^T$

A facial image can be projected in to 1D subspace

Weight matrix = $W_i = [\Omega_1 \ \Omega_2 \ \dots \ \Omega_M]^T$

Compute the threshold value

$$\theta = \frac{1}{2} \max\{\|\Omega_i - \Omega_j\|\} \text{ for } i, j = 1 \dots M$$

II Testing Phase

Consider a recognizing or unknown image r for testing

$$r = \begin{bmatrix} r_1 & r_2 & r_3 \\ r_4 & r_5 & r_6 \\ r_7 & r_8 & r_{N^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{or } r = [r_1 \ r_2 \ r_3 \ r_4 \ r_5 \ r_6 \ r_7 \ r_8 \ r_{N^2}]^T = rX1 = \begin{bmatrix} r_1 \\ r_2 \\ r_3 \\ \vdots \\ r_{N^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\vec{r}_m = \begin{bmatrix} r_1 - m_1 \\ r_2 - m_2 \\ \vdots \\ r_{N^2} - m_{N^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

Compute the covariance matrix C , by referring above steps. Where $C = \vec{r}_m^T \vec{r}_m$ Consider a testing image r_m (recognizing image) repeat the step1 to step 6 as given above. And compute the projection on to the face space.

$$W_r = U^T (\vec{r}_m)$$

Where \vec{r}_m is a average subspace image of testing image.

III Score Value calculation Phase (Classification using Euclidean distance)

Compute distance in the face space between the testing face and training face images.

$\epsilon_i^2 = \|W_r - W_i\|^2$ for all $i=1 \dots M$ Where W_i is a vector describing the k^{th} face class of training images. If ϵ_i is less than some predefined threshold value θ_i or if $\min\{\epsilon_i\} < \theta$ then test image belongs to class i . So that recognizing image is matched with trained image.

Architecture I

Rows of S are independent basis images, which combined by A yield the input images X . Learning W allows us to estimate the basis images in the rows of U . In practice, for reasons of computational tractability, PCA is first performed on the input data X to find the top K eigenfaces; these are arranged in the columns of a matrix S . Then ICA is performed on S^T ; that is, the images are variables, and the pixel values are observations. Let C be the PCA coefficient matrix, that is, $X = CS^T$. Then the k independent component analysis basis images are estimated by the rows of $U = WS^T$, and the coefficients for the data are computed from $X = SW^{-1} U$.

Figure 3. Blind source separation model

Figure 4. 2D data representation and the corresponding component axes a) principal components and b) independent component axes

Architecture II

This architecture assumes that the sources in S are independent co-efficient, and the columns of the mixing matrix A are the basis images; that is, the variables in the source separation problem are the pixels. Similar to Architecture I, ICA is preceded by PCA; however, in this case the input to ICA is the coefficient matrix C . The resulting ICA basis consists of the columns of SA and the coefficients are found in the rows of $U = WC^T$. These coefficients give the factorial representation of the data. Figure 5 shows image synthesis model of ICA based face recognition. Generally, the bases obtained with Architecture I reflect more local properties of the faces; whereas the bases in Architecture II have global properties and much more resemble faces[16].

Figure 5. Image synthesis model for ICA face recognition

c. Singular Value Decomposition

Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) is based on a theorem from linear algebra which says that a singular value matrix W can be represented by the product of three matrices, an orthogonal matrix U is a square matrix, a diagonal matrix D , and the transpose of an orthogonal matrix V is a square matrix [15]. The theorem is usually presented as $W = UDV^T$

Columns of matrix U are orthonormal eigenvectors of W or covariance matrix C . Similarly the columns of V are orthonormal eigenvectors of W^T , and D is a diagonal matrix containing the square roots of eigenvalues from U or V in descending order. Implementation of SVD method is illustrated in the following steps.

SVD Algorithm

I Training phase

Step 1: Compute the covariance matrix

Refer step 1 to step 4 of PCA algorithm and compute the covariance matrix, which is given by

$$C = AA^T$$

Step 2: Compute the eigenvectors

U and V are eigenvectors of covariance matrix C , in this experiment all the images are considered as square matrix. U and V are eigenvalues of m by m orthogonal square matrix because $m=n$, Compute the diagonal matrix D , it is a square roots of eigenvalues of U or V in descending order.

Step 3: Compute Singular Value decomposition value of training images ie

$$W_i = UDV^T$$

II Testing Phase

Compute the covariance matrix C , eigenvectors U , V and diagonal matrix D by referring above steps.

Where $C = \overline{r_m}$ (i, where $\overline{r_m}$ is same as found in PCA algorithm. U and V are orthonormal eigenvectors of C , where D is a diagonal matrix of either V or U . Compute Singular value decomposition value of testing image

$$W_r = U$$

III Calculation of Euclidean distance

Compute distance in the face space between the testing face and training face images.

$$\epsilon_i^2 = \|W_r - W_i\|^2 \text{ for all } i=1 \dots M,$$

Where W_i is a vector describing the k^{th} face class of training images. If ϵ_i is less than some predefined threshold value θ or if $\min\{\epsilon_i\} < \theta$ then test image belongs to class i . So that recognizing image is matched with trained image.

d. Locality Preserving Projections

Locality Preserving Projections (LPP) is an unsupervised manifold dimensionality reduction approach, here linear projective maps that arise by solving a variation problem that optimally preserves the

neighbourhood structure of the data set. In this method higher dimensional vectors obtained by concatenating consecutive static feature vectors are projected to a low dimensional subspace which aims to find the optimal projection matrix W by minimizing the following criterion function:

$$J_1(W) = \sum_{i,j} \|y_i - y_j\|^2 S_{ij}.$$

Substituting $y_i = W^T x_i$ into above objection function. Direct computation yields

$$J_1(W) = 2\text{trace}(W^T XLX^T W),$$

Where $L=D-S$ is called Laplacian matrix, D is a diagonal matrix defined by

$$D = \text{diag} \{D_{11}, D_{22}, \dots, D_{NN}\}$$

where $D_{ii} = \sum_j S_{ij}$. Matrix D provides a natural measure on the data points. The bigger the value D_{ii} (corresponding to y_i) more important is y_i . Thereby, the projection matrix W should maximize the following constraint objective function simultaneously:

$$\begin{aligned} J_2(W) &= \sum_{i=1}^N y_i^T D y_i = \text{trace}(Y^T D Y) \\ &= \text{trace}(W^T X D X^T W). \end{aligned}$$

Solving problems $\min J_1(W)$ and $\max J_2(W)$ simultaneously is equivalent to minimizing the following criterion function:

$$J(W) = \frac{\text{trace}(W^T XLX^T W)}{\text{trace}(W^T X D X^T W)},$$

The optimal locality preserving projection matrix

$$W_{LPP} = \arg \min_{W \in R^{d \times d}} J(W)$$

This can be obtained by solving the following generalized eigenvalue problem:

$$XLX^T W = (X D X^T) W \Lambda.$$

where is Λ a diagonal eigenvalue matrix. While in most cases, the number of training data is smaller than the dimension of feature vector, i.e. $d \ll N$. When this 3S problem occurs, the matrix $X D X^T$ is not full rank.

LPP Algorithm

Step 1: Start

Step 2: Construct neighborhood graph G .

Step 3: Use k-nearest neighbor criterion and ϵ -ball neighborhood graph.

Step 4: Perform Edge weight assignment.

Step 5: Applying simple-mind

Step 6: Solve the generalized eigenvalue problems.

Step 7: End

e. Fisher Face Analysis

Fisher Face analysis explicitly attempts to model the difference between the classes of pixel data. It is a Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) a powerful face recognition method that overcomes the limitation of Principle Component Analysis method by applying the linear discriminant criterion[18]. This criterion tries to maximize the ratio of the determinant of the between-class scatter matrix of the projected samples to the determinant of the within class scatter matrix of the projected samples. Linear discriminant group images of the same class and separates images of different classes of the images. This method is developed in 1997 by P. Belhumeur et al. It is based on Fisher’s Linear Discriminant Analysis. Faster than eigenfaces, in some cases it has lower error rates works well even if different illumination, works well even if different facial expression. LDA seeks directions that are efficient for discrimination between the data [19]. LDA maximizes the between-class scatter and minimizes the within-class scatter. The LDA method tries to find the subspace that discriminates different face classes. The within-class scatter matrix is also called intra personal means variation in appearance of the same individual due to different lighting and face expression. The between-class scatter matrix also called the extra personal represents variation in appearance due to difference in identity. Linear discriminant methods group images of the same classes and separates images of the different classes. To identify an input test image, the projected test image is compared to each projected training image, and the test image is identified as the closest training image.

Let us consider set of N sample images ie $\{X_1, X_2, X_3, \dots, X_n\}$, taking in n -dimensional image space and assume that each image belongs to one of c classes $\{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_c\}$.

Let N_i be the number of samples in class C_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, c$), and $\mu_i = \frac{1}{N_i} \sum_{X \in C_i} X$, where μ_i be the mean of the samples in class C_i , and $\mu = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N X_i$, where μ be the mean of all samples. Then the between class scatter matrix S_B is defined as

$$S_B = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^c N_i (\mu_i - \mu) (\mu_i - \mu)^T$$

Similarly within the class scatter matrix S_W is defined as

$$S_W = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{X_k \in C_i} (X_i - \mu_i) (X_i - \mu_i)^T$$

Consider 8 images with different expressions of different classes ie a, b, c up to h of different classes.

FF Algorithm

I. Training Phase

Step 1: Compute the average face

Consider a square image with width=height = N from image database, M is the total number of images in training database and P is the number of persons in the database (number of classes).

Repeat the step 1 as explained in PCA algorithm.

Step 2: Compute the average face of each person

$$\vec{x} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} a_1 + b_1 \\ a_2 + b_2 \\ \vdots \\ a_{N^2} + b_{N^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad \vec{y} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} c_1 + d_1 \\ c_2 + d_2 \\ \vdots \\ c_{N^2} + d_{N^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad \vec{z} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} e_1 + f_1 \\ e_2 + f_2 \\ \vdots \\ e_{N^2} + f_{N^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad \vec{w} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} g_1 + h_1 \\ g_2 + h_2 \\ \vdots \\ g_{N^2} + h_{N^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

Step 3: Subtract average value from the training faces

$$\vec{a}_m = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 - x_1 \\ a_2 - x_2 \\ \vdots \\ a_{N^2} - x_{N^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad \vec{b}_m = \begin{bmatrix} b_1 - x_1 \\ b_2 - x_2 \\ \vdots \\ b_{N^2} - x_{N^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad \vec{c}_m = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 - y_1 \\ c_2 - y_2 \\ \vdots \\ c_{N^2} - y_{N^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad \vec{d}_m = \begin{bmatrix} d_1 - y_1 \\ d_2 - y_2 \\ \vdots \\ d_{N^2} - y_{N^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\vec{e}_m = \begin{bmatrix} e_1 - z_1 \\ e_2 - z_2 \\ \vdots \\ e_{N^2} - z_{N^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad \vec{f}_m = \begin{bmatrix} f_1 - z_1 \\ f_2 - z_2 \\ \vdots \\ f_{N^2} - z_{N^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad \vec{g}_m = \begin{bmatrix} g_1 - w_1 \\ g_2 - w_2 \\ \vdots \\ g_{N^2} - w_{N^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad \vec{h}_m = \begin{bmatrix} h_1 - w_1 \\ h_2 - w_2 \\ \vdots \\ h_{N^2} - w_{N^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

Step 4: Build scatter matrices S₁, S₂, S₃, S₄

$$S_1 = (\vec{a}_m \vec{a}_m^T + \vec{b}_m \vec{b}_m^T) \quad S_2 = (\vec{c}_m \vec{c}_m^T + \vec{d}_m \vec{d}_m^T)$$

$$S_3 = (\vec{e}_m \vec{e}_m^T + \vec{f}_m \vec{f}_m^T) \quad S_4 = (\vec{g}_m \vec{g}_m^T + \vec{h}_m \vec{h}_m^T)$$

The **within-class scatter matrix S_w**

$$S_w = S_1 + S_2 + S_3 + S_4$$

The **between-class scatter matrix**

$$S_B = 2(\vec{x} - \vec{m})(\vec{x} - \vec{m})^T + 2(\vec{y} - \vec{m})(\vec{y} - \vec{m})^T + 2(\vec{z} - \vec{m})(\vec{z} - \vec{m})^T + 2(\vec{w} - \vec{m})(\vec{w} - \vec{m})^T$$

The class isolation can be measured by a certain criterion. A commonly used one is the ratio of the determinant of the between-class scatter matrix of the projected samples to the within-class scatter matrix of the projected samples.

Step 6: Maximizing the matrix W

$$J(W_i) = \frac{|W^T S_B W|}{|W^T S_w W|}$$

Step 7: Compute the threshold value

$$\theta = \frac{1}{2} \max\{|\Omega_i - \Omega_j|\} \text{ for } i, j = 1 \dots M$$

II Testing Phase: Consider a recognizing or unknown image *r* for testing

$$r = \begin{bmatrix} r_1 & r_2 & r_3 \\ r_4 & r_5 & r_6 \\ r_7 & r_8 & r_{N^2} \end{bmatrix} = r = [r_1 \ r_2 \ r_3 \ r_4 \ r_5 \ r_6 \ r_7 \ r_8 \ r_{N^2}]^T = rX1 = \begin{bmatrix} r_1 \\ r_2 \\ r_3 \\ \vdots \\ r_{N^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\vec{r}_m = \begin{bmatrix} r_1 - m_1 \\ r_2 - m_2 \\ \vdots \\ r_{N^2} - m_{N^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

Compute the covariance matrix *C*, by referring above steps. Where $C = \vec{r}_m(i)$.

Consider a testing image *r_m* (recognizing image) repeat the step1 to step 4 as given above. And compute the projection on to the face space.

$$W_r = U^T (\vec{r}_m), \text{ where } \vec{r}_m \text{ is a average subspace image of testing image.}$$

III Score Value calculation Phase (Classification using Euclidean distance)

Compute distance in the face space between the testing face and training face images.

$$\epsilon_i^2 = \|W_r - W_i\|^2 \text{ for all } i=1 \dots M$$

Where *W_i* is a vector describing the *kth* face class of training images. If ϵ_i is less than some predefined threshold value θ_i or if $\min\{\epsilon_i\} < \theta$ then test image belongs to class *i*. So that recognizing image is matched with trained image.

3. Conclusion

Dimensionality reduction and finding the coefficients vectors are essential steps in appearance based methods for facial expression recognition. Various methods have been illustrated in this paper concludes that PCA, ICA and LPP methods are unsupervised subspace analysis because it does not needs any class labels hence computation time decreases. We have observed that Fisher Face Analysis is a supervised subspace learning method it needs class labels separation. Projection coefficients vectors are considered as feature vectors and these vectors used for facial expression recognition. After the observation of all the above subspace methods Euclidean distance between feature vectors should be less than predefined threshold value calculated by considering vectors of weight matrix. If this distance value is less than threshold value then recognition accuracy has been is increased.

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